

Deweyan Democratic Values: A Framework for Music Education

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Abstract

For John Dewey, the fate of democracy rested on the shoulders of education. As the preeminent educational reformer of the 20th century, he advocated for experimentation, creativity and the development of students as 'reflexive' thinkers; he prized the pooling of collective and cooperative experience, and saw it as imperative for progressively generating the knowledge and wisdom needed to transcend dogmas and "guide collective action." Dewey's progressive philosophies on education and art are still relevant today and remain deeply embedded within educational discourse. However, the field of music education has been hesitant to integrate Dewey's ideas of democratic education into the classroom while maintaining largely a traditionalist approach. A rapidly changing music education landscape calls for the revisiting of Dewey's ground breaking ideas. This paper (1) briefly examines the current state of American formal music education, then (2) explores Deweyan democratic values as a framework for music education, and finally (3) envisions practical applications for the field.

Preprint

Deweyan Democratic Values: A Framework for Music Education

John Dewey (1859-1952) was an American philosopher and one of the most influential American intellectuals of the first half of the 20th century. His influence reached across the globe with writings spanning the realms of metaphysics, epistemology, logic, aesthetics, ethics and the philosophy of religion; further, his impact on educational philosophy is indelible. For Dewey, the fate of a democracy rested on the shoulders of education (Hildebrand, 2018). As a leader in the progressive educational movement of the 20th century, Dewey advocated for experimentation, creativity and the development of students as ‘reflexive’ thinkers. This philosophy has often been referred to as a ‘child-centered’ approach. He saw children as natural scientists with “the native and unspoiled attitude of childhood, marked by ardent curiosity, fertile imagination, and love of experimental inquiry,” and further noting its similarity to “the attitude of the scientific mind.” (Dewey, 1910b, p.179; as cited in Woodford, 2015). Dewey’s progressive philosophies on education and art are still relevant today and remain prominent across educational discourse. However, the field of music education has been hesitant to integrate Dewey’s ideas of democratic education into the classroom. This paper (1) briefly examines the current state of American formal music education, then (2) explores Deweyan democratic values as a framework for music education, and finally (3) envisions practical applications for the field.

For Dewey, successful democracy was dependent on the education of its citizens. The role of education was to prepare students to participate and thus contribute to the common good (Woodford, 2005). The concept of democracy transcended politics, manifesting as an “ethical ideal” and “communal way of life” (Dewey, 1888, p.41). Democracy necessarily required the participation of every mature citizen, (Dewey, 1991) and further, education should free the mind, allowing citizens to fully participate in civic duties. Moreover, Dewey prized the pooling of collective and cooperative experience, and saw it as imperative for progressively generating the knowledge and wisdom needed to “guide collective action” (Dewey, 1991, p. 402). Dewey ultimately sought a world of free thinking individuals who had the skills to overcome “past experience, received dogmas, the stirring of self-interest, the arousing of passion, sheer

mental laziness, a false social environment steeped in biased traditions or animated by false expectations, and so on” (Dewey, 1910b, p.141-42). The seeds of free thinking and collective action were planted in education.

Current State of Music Education

Despite Dewey’s early progressivism, traditionalist educational philosophies remain dominant in modern music education through its genre standards, repertoire choices, and ensemble power structures. The core of traditional or ‘formal’ education involves the passing down of facts, ideas, beliefs from one generation to the next. In essence, education is the locus of transmission for knowledge and artifacts deemed worthy within a particular culture (Thomas, 2013, p.25). In the United States this model of transmission has been perpetuated since the inception of music education in the mid 19th century. ‘Formal’ music education can be defined as “educational institutions” such as primary schools, conservatories, secondary schools or universities that are “entirely dedicated to the teaching and learning of music” (Green, 2002, p.4). The dominant culture has deemed European art music traditions and knowledge regarding bands, orchestras, and choirs to be worthy of preservation through these institutions. Moreover, institutional western art music traditions in the U.S have historically been conservative class-based endeavors used for indoctrination (Woodford, 2005), and assimilation (Hill, 1892; Gramit, 2014; Campbell, et al. 2019) to hegemonic culture.

The nature of formal music education is not rooted in innovation, but rather in the replication of the past. (Allsup, 2011). Bands, orchestras and choirs, and the music they play, are what Allsup (2016) calls closed forms, where traditions are unalterable and preserved in their original state. Moreover, the power structures within these ensembles are almost exclusively hierarchical with power centralized in the director or teacher. Further, decision making regarding repertoire, dynamics, tempos, articulations and expressions are made solely by the individual in power. This model of music education has produced countless virtuosos in the western classical canon, however these traditions and their embodied

pedagogical methods may not be preparing students with the skills needed to optimally participate in a modern democratic society.

Deweyan Democratic Values as a Framework for Music Education

Dewey saw teachers as moral and intellectual leaders who establish conditions for learning. Educators were at the forefront of producing democracy's free thinking population. He did not speak specifically to music pedagogy, however Deweyan educational concepts can be distilled into a framework for musical teaching and learning; select relevant concepts include, (1) teachers as facilitators, (2) students as 'reflective' thinkers (now referred to as critical thinkers), and (3) students as creators of collective communal values. Moreover, special attention is paid to the work of Randall Allsup and his significant contributions in elucidating the importance and applications of Dewey's work in contemporary music education.

In Dewey's eyes, ideal teachers were not dictators, but facilitators who were meant to guide students in the learning process. The ideal learning environment was one where students could become actively engaged with themselves and others, building off of past experiences. He believed students were not passive receptacles for information, but rather active participants in knowledge creation; the learning environment must be more like a laboratory, with "a spirit of free communication" and an "interchange of ideas, suggestions, [and] results," and where students embody "both successes and failures of previous experiences." (Dewey, 1899, p.32). To Dewey, learning happened naturally through life, and students' personal experiences were central to the process.

"...we learn from experience, and from books or the sayings of others *only* as they are related to experience...not mere phrases" (Dewey, 1899, p. 31.)

Students create knowledge through active participation in relating old experiences to new ones; this does not happen through the passive absorption of isolated facts, e.g. learning musical scales and intervals removed from a familiar musical context, or learning musical pieces that are far removed from students' interests or previous knowledge base. It was the teachers' responsibility to help students make relevant

connections. Creating spaces for students to encounter new personally significant experiences requires an open-ended approach to teaching. “The educator cannot start with knowledge already organized and proceed to ladle it out in doses” (Dewey, Allsup 2016, p.93); i.e., planning only goes so far, and closed and unalterable traditions of teaching must be open to new ways of exploring music that appeal to what Dewey referred to as students’ “natural resources.” Dewey outlined natural resources as:

1. *Communication*. the social aspect of learning: the urge to share
2. *Inquiry*. Asking questions and solving problems: the desire to find out.
3. *Construction*. Shaping materials, finding divergent means: the need to make.
4. *Artistic expression*. The aesthetic domain: the urge to say something new, to reveal an aspect of one’s self.

Dewey suggested that teachers are neglecting students’ inherent strengths if they appeal to anything less than these four natural resources (Allsup, 2016, p.94). Teachers must give up the role of the dictator to let students explore democratically. He thought instructions should be “full, free, and flexible” with a “social motive.” (Dewey, 1899, p.31) The facilitator’s role was to cultivate students’ natural urge for exploration and creation, as their “instinct of investigation seems to grow out of the combination of the constructive impulse with the conversational” (Dewey, 1899, 34). Expanding on Dewey’s concept of a ‘learning laboratory’ (Dewey, 1930), Allsup (2016) connected it to music education, outlining six propositions:

1. A linear structure of music teaching is not the only vision we can permit or imagine; a closed structure of music teaching is not the only vision we can permit or imagine.
2. Learning does not need to be visible or be made visible to account for its meaning or impact.
3. There is no inherent contradiction between an open classroom and a structured plan of action
4. A teacher-dominated structure can never fully capture the richness and complexity of a student-initiated quest.

The teacher has more, not fewer, responsibilities in an open classroom than in one that is closed.

It is more difficult to be a laboratory facilitator than it is to be a master.

In conflict with a traditionalist view of education, these six progressive propositions provide a roadmap to a more democratic way of music teaching and learning. However, manifesting these propositions may be difficult to implement given the natural limitations of formal schooling structures.

Reflective thinking becomes imperative as students are given more freedom to make decisions and work democratically. Reflective thinking at its heart, involves criticism. The ability to critique existing structures and traditions through a thoughtful valuation. Dewey noted that it's the best option, citing reflective thinking as "a better method than its alternatives, authority, imitation, caprice, and ignorance, prejudice and passion" (Dewey, 1917; as cited in Woodford, p.18). Education should lead to the development of autonomy and a self-realization of students' potential. In music education, teachers can encourage students to think critically on a microlevel, questioning the notes, rhythms, dynamics, articulations and instruments they are playing. Moreover, students can be further encouraged to transcend the notes and rhythms and apply critique on a macrolevel. Dewey was particularly against dogmatic practices, especially those based on a prior assumption of authority. Students should be inspired to examine the social and historical contexts of repertoire choices, and question the moral merits of the music they play and the way they play it. This line of questioning may even lead to a critique of the oppressive systems which determine the nature of the educational experience (Freire, 2018), e.g. the ever-present settler colonial structures that preserve band, orchestra and choir within formal schooling.

Through democratic participation, powered by reflective thinking, students can begin to forge collective communal musical values. In *Art as Experience*, Dewey spoke to the importance of knowing many artistic traditions and conditions in which art is made, thus leading to an openness in the process of artistic valuation.

Through knowledge of a variety of conditions, the critic becomes aware of the vast variety of materials that are usable (since they have been used) in art. He is saved from the snap judgment that this or that work is esthetically wrong because it has matter to which he is not accustomed, and when he comes across a work whose matter has no discoverable precedent he will be wary of uttering an offhand condemnation. *Since form is always integral with matter, he will also, if his own experience is genuinely esthetic, appreciate the multitude of special forms that exist and be safeguarded against identifying form with some technique that he has come to prefer.* In short, not only will his general background be broadened, but he will become familiar, to the point of saturation, with a more fundamental matter, the conditions under which the subject-matter of varied modes of experience move to fulfillment. And this movement constitutes the objective and publicly accessible content of all works of art (Dewey, 1980, p. 311).

Dewey argued that through the absorption of diverse styles and ways of artistic creation, one becomes familiar with a collection of values that can be used to develop greater understanding for the value of artistic works that may be disparate from the critic's natural preferences. In essence he's elucidating the subjective nature of aesthetic values and advocating for a form of artistic, and by extension musical pluralism. In the music room these principles can manifest in the exploration of diverse musical styles of the local and the global. In Dewey's eyes, the greater musical diversity that students encounter, the more influences they have to thoughtfully craft their own aesthetic values.

Dewey's ideas assert that students have the right and the ability to craft their own values as young musicians communally making music, and they should be liberated to define their aesthetic terms through the process of discovery, exploring different ways to organize sound. It is through this communal process that students may find truth in their creations. Dewey defined truth as the state of things "as they are, not as they are in the inane and desolate void of isolation from human concern, but as they are in a shared and progressive experience" (Dewey 1978, p. 67; as cited in Hildebrand, 2018). Students creating music in the moment have found truth in their creations or their musical aesthetic by nature of experiencing the

moment. Similarly, Dewey evoked this same reasoning in *Art as Experience* to justify his wariness of traditions saying “even a crude experience, if authentically an experience, is more fit to give a clue to the intrinsic nature of esthetic experience than is an object already set apart from any other mode of experience” (Dewey, 1980, p.11). It was important to resist exclusively imitating the masters and replicating past artifacts for the sake of tradition. Allowing students creating music through a process of discovery, was inherently more authentic than perpetuating or reproducing past works. Music educators can encourage this process by exposing students to diverse musical styles and genres from around the world, allowing students to relate new musical experiences to their own musical traditions, and enabling students to create new music together through a process of collectively crafting communal values.

Practical Applications for the Field

This paper now envisions practical applications of Deweyan principles in music education as an attempt to validate non-traditional musical pedagogies that have been shown to actively engage students in ways that more traditional transmission-based pedagogies do not. Dewey was one of American pragmatism’s early founders (Hildebrand, 2018). Broadly, pragmatist philosophy understands “knowing of the word as inseparable from agency within it” (Legg & Hookway, 2020, p.1), i.e., a theory’s value is intrinsically connected to its practical applications. Applications of democratic learning are primarily found in informal music teaching and learning in settings such as rock music or ‘community music’ (Green 2002, Campbell, 2019), however Deweyan ideas of democratic education have been used in schools through the use of similar non-traditional pedagogies. This section suggests collective composition and collective songwriting pedagogy as practical ways to embody Dewey’s concepts and create an active learning environment of discovery by embracing (1) teacher as facilitator, (2) students as reflective thinkers, and (3) students as creators of collective communal values.

Collective Composition

“When students are given space to explore freely, to work democratically, they will create (from their musical worlds) a context about which they are familiar, conversant, or curious.” (Allsup, 2003, p.35).

John Dewey’s principles of teachers as facilitators, student’s as reflective thinkers and shapers of communal values all manifest in-school and outside of school collective composition activities. Rock music in particular has long been associated with democratic styles of music teaching and learning. The music movement was birthed and cultivated from the “garage,” where musicians would collectively craft their sound, negotiating their sonic identity through explorations of melody, harmony, articulation, dynamics, tempo, lyrics and more. The musicians engage in what Dewey called a “shared and progressive experience” toward finding a sonic truth (Dewey, 1978, p.67; as cited in Hildebrand, 2018). Often these musical sessions are composed of young developing musicians who mold unconventional spaces into optimal learning environments. Commenting on this phenomenon, Allsup (2011) posited that “what popular musicians do in garage bands is more or less a natural combination of sound education practices, like creative music making and group problem solving, only minus a coach or teacher” (p.31).

In a formal music setting, students can collaborate, create, and work democratically in non-obligatory, self-directed, and personally meaningful ways, given the proper conditions. A study by Allsup (2003) investigated students' capacity for “discovery” and “democratic action” in a learning environment governed by the democratic principles of garage bands. Students were divided into two groups, one with students on their primary concert band instruments, and the other with rock band instruments (electric guitar, bass, synthesized piano, and drums). Dewey’s values were imparted to students as they were to create a piece of music that was “meaningful and self-reflective.” The teacher became a facilitator rather than an authoritarian, while students, responding to the nature of the assignment, were forced to embrace Deweyan ideas of thinking reflectively and negotiating collectively to forge distinct communal musical values. Throughout the process, themes of interpersonal relationships, peer learning, peer critique and mutual care emerged. “Democratic learning,” where power is negotiated

through shared decision making (Beadie, 1996; Jorgensen, 2001; Allsup, 2003) took place in the creation of original collective compositions. Allsup describes how the group with popular music instruments conveyed their opinions through improvisation on their instruments in what Dewey would refer to as “a spirit of free communication” with an “interchange of ideas, suggestions,” and “results” (Dewey, 1899, p.32). It was a constant sonic conversation, where musical ideas or riffs were put forth and built upon in layers. Garage bands usually have a leader (Campbell, 1995; Finnagan, 1989; Green, 2002, Allsup, 2003); this is often due to the inherent difference in skill levels among group members with the most experienced taking the lead. However, true to Deweyan ideals, everyone had a role to play as active participants. The groups worked cohesively and democratically, and ultimately created a piece that was appreciated by participants and well received by the audience.

Allsup’s (2003) study showed the positive impact that democratic music making can have on learners. When the teacher relinquishes authority it creates space for students to think reflectively and collectively, and ultimately craft musical values democratically. This process evokes what Dewey calls students’ natural resources—*communication, inquiry, construction and artistic expression*. When engaging with these natural resources students learn from each other as exemplified by Julie, a girl from the Allsup (2003) study who in a post music-making reflection stated, “I think you can learn better from your peers than you can from your teacher (p.22).” Recalling the traditional versus progressive educational dichotomy, learning focused less on transmission (one student teaching another student guitar fingerings) and more on the process of discovery (creating chord progression together), with Allsup stating that “participants discovered more than to the input of their peers” (p.33). Teaching as a facilitator requires trust, and demands that the teacher teaches *with* their students rather than *to* their students. However, it’s important to note that teachers still have an inherent degree of authority given the power differential associated with traditional musical knowledge.

Collective Songwriting

Collective songwriting has emerged as a viable pedagogy, in and outside of school that exemplifies Deweyan values of democratic education. The process has been evidenced by a series of case studies involving a tribal-compact school in eastern Washington (Campbell et al, 2019; Igari et al, 2020). Rooted in a process utilized by Chicano activist-artist(artivistas), collective songwriting first asks participants to deeply reflect on their lived experiences and community concerns in *atestimonio*, or “an expression of life views, triumphs, aphorism, and struggles” ultimately manifesting in song lyrics (Gonzalez, 2015, p.131). The lyrics are then set to original music created and negotiated by the group. The teacher becomes more of a *facilitator* through the process, looking to students and their lived experiences as catalysts for inspiration, creativity and music-making. Moreover, collective songwriting forces students to *think reflectively* about their lives and their communities, and through the process, craft *communal values* in the form of a song. The process further exemplifies Deweyan ideas by exposing students to diverse musical styles and genres from around the world, employing pedagogy that is responsive to students’ previous musical experiences, and by encouraging the collective creation of new musical aesthetics through a synthesis of students’ experiences.

Collective songwriting, in its essence, centers what Dewey referred to as the “ideal of a continuous reconstruction or reorganizing of experience,” which leads to the increase of its recognized meaning or social content and can “increase the capacity of individuals to act as directive guardians of this reorganization” (Dewey, 2001, p. 331). Testimonio begins with students individually and collectively reflecting on their lived experiences and offering them to the group as seeds of a collective song; “this act of sharing individual and community concerns manifests in a tree of ideas, with one thought branching out into many more, produced by collective minds, and sprawling across a large whiteboard” (Igari, et al, 2020, p.71). During the project, the teacher(s) acted as facilitators who are not transmitting traditions, but rather guiding students in the creation of new ones. Valuing student agency and voice was at the center of these classes (Igari et al, 2020). Facilitators used clarifying questions and would summarize students’ contributions in effort to provoke deeper conversation (Campbell et al, 2019). Further, student’s were

prompted *to think reflectively* through the facilitators' strategic questioning, for example., "what's important to you?" and "what are issues in your community." Through semi-guided discussions, the recurring themes became clear. (e.g. land rights, cultural loss, harm to the environment emerged (Campbell et al, 2019), alcoholism, and MMIW [murdered and missing indigenous women]). Scattered ideas became solidified into lyrical phrases. This is the type of learning that Dewey imagined when stating that "...we learn from experience, and from books or the sayings of others *only* as they are related to experience...not mere phrases" (Dewey, 1899, p.31), i.e., students' lived experiences are crucial materials for creating new musical knowledge in the classroom. These collectively negotiated themes and phrases eventually unveil a collective epistemology and an elucidation of distinct communal values. Further, the process of *testimonio* is a "powerful exercise in consensus building and collective knowledge production" (Gonzalez, 2015, p. 131), or in the words of Dewey, a "shared progressive experience" towards truth.

The next phase puts students' collectively composed lyrics to music. The process began with students bringing in music that they enjoy or identify with (e.g., rock, hip hop, pop, country) (Igari et al, 2020). In defining artistic values, Dewey spoke to the importance of exposing oneself to other ways of defining art, or other "modes of experiences" to the point where different perspectives become "familiar to the point of saturation" (Dewey, 1980, p.311)—it is then, that student can create new values. In the collective songwriting process, student's listened to many styles of music to determine what is valuable to them. The process then gave rise to the intersectional identities and values of the collective. In both Campbell et al, (2019, and Igari et al, (2020), students found themselves at the cultural crossroad of their communities' traditional practices and popular youth culture norms.

Student autonomy and musical exploration are central to collective songwriting. In the creative process students investigated different instruments and different styles. Dewey saw this as exploiting students' "native tendencies to explore, to manipulate tools and materials, to construct, to give expression to joyous emotion" and more (Dewey, 2001, p. 202). They are encouraged to experiment with instruments

and incorporate musics from outside of school that they may not know how to play. Dewey saw this as a way to get “the whole pupil engaged” and bridge “the artificial gap between life in school and out” (p.202). Some students strummed guitars and ukuleles, while others decided to rap or haphazardly create with digital audio workstations and computer synthesizers. The process concluded with a collectively written song and a performance, both of which serve as manifestations of reflective thought and negotiated values. While the project resulted in a sharable artifact, Dewey might say that the aim of this type of project “is not the economic value of the products, but the development of social power and insight” (Dewey, 1966, p. 32).

Conclusion

Images of a progressive music education that prioritizes future innovation over replications of the past emerges as we imagine Deweyan principles as foundations for music teaching. Dewey’s overarching logic derived from his belief that successful democracy is dependent on a free thinking citizenry that possesses the intellectual tools to fully participate. He asserted that teachers play an integral role in developing this vision, i.e., preparing students for democratic action. If we accept the proposition that education should cultivate reflective thinkers who engage in democratic action, we must look at current pedagogical trends in music education with a critical eye and ask whether they are helpful in meeting this objective. The aforementioned practical manifestations of Deweyan ideals (Allsup, 2003; Campbell et al, 2019; Igari et al, 2020) have shown that pedagogies perpetuating democratic action in students is valuable, and can be done in a formal school setting where students work together to collaborate, negotiate and innovate. The transmission-based paradigm of band, orchestra and choir still dominates school music nationwide, however exclusively focusing on the replication of past art may be doing students a disservice in a rapidly changing world.

Pushing forward to new paradigms in music education is important in order to meet the demands of an evolving society. Democratic music education has the potential to prepare students for success in society following graduation from formal schooling. The outcomes of collective composition and

collective songwriting result in a collaborative and distinct musical product that has been thoughtfully sculpted through the collaborative negotiation of musical values. Such pedagogies utilize students' natural resources (i.e. communication, inquiry, construction, and artistic expression) and advocate for critical thinking and creativity; they ultimately prepare students to not only participate in democracy, but to thrive in a quickly changing technological world, marked by innovation, where new ideas are prized above all else. Outside of the 'western art music education' paradigm, reflective thinking, musical autonomy, and creativity are incredibly important. Academically speaking, creativity (improvisation and composition) is the most complex of cognitive processes, where students create, generate, plan and produce (Hanna, 2007). Pedagogies like collective composition or collective songwriting push students to work at their highest cognitive capacities, helping prepare them to succeed in society after graduation. Moreover, future jobs in all domains, including music, will reward those who can negotiate, and innovate, and those who resort to the recitation of facts or traditional knowledge will be replaced by automation, unable to meet the demands of society. The changes taking place can already be seen in the music market, with high fidelity sampling replacing studio musicians and orchestras, and highly trained singers losing gigs to creative amateurs with autotune. The changes can even be observed at the local pub that has recently fired their local cover band in exchange for a DJ. The music industry at large has changed dramatically over the last three decades, in part due to rapid technological advances. Music education is still operating on an old paradigm, and the integration of Dewey's principles of democratic education are worthy of consideration, as they may be able to incite the transformation needed to meet the constantly evolving societal landscape, and most importantly, prepare students to participate in democratic action.

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